

UB2030 | KNOWLEDGE HUB

A TREND REPORT ON THE FUTURE OF THE RESEARCH LIBRARY IN 2030

Presentation for VU MJP session | July 2025 |
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OBJECTIVES, ACTIVITIES & PLANNING

Objective: Provide management team insights in emerging trends (e.g. academic sovereignty) and technologies (e.g. applied AI) in the academic knowledge creation cycle, for strategic decision making for future procurement and project portfolio

Co-creation: Innovation is not done alone. Creating a culture of innovation is done together.

Method: Each month, a series of semi-structured interviews with people in a department will be conducted on their vision for the future.

Deliverables: Podcast interviews & Trend Report

For each Head of Department

Pre-interview survey

- Latest trends in your department
- Your innovation hero (external)

Interview

- Invite hero
- Method: Future's triangle
- Podcast release

Report

- Key findings
- Recommendations / next steps

PODCAST | [HTTPS://UBVU.GITHUB.IO/UB2030/](https://ubvu.github.io/ub2030/)

VU Library Live

UB2030 - Toekomst van Universiteitsbibliothe...

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Toekomst van Universiteitsbibliotheken - een introductie

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Toekomst van Open Science

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Future of Digital Library Services and Infrastructures (in English)

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Toekomst van Research Intelligence

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Toekomst van Research Data en Software Management

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Future of Research Support (in English)

VU Library Live - UB2030 - Future of Education Support

VU Library Live
UB2030 - The Future of Research Libraries

TITLE (WITH LINK)	GUESTS	DESCRIPTION	DATE	LISTENERS
UB2030 - FUTURE OF RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT	Tim Pinchetti (Enterprise Architect, VU), Meron Vermaas (Coordinator RSM, VU), Marcel Ras (Coordinator RDM Network, VU)	The podcast delves into the current state, challenges, and future directions of research data and software management, emphasising their importance for the integrity, transparency, and efficiency of scientific research.	2023-03-12	66
UB2030 - FUTURE OF RESEARCH INTELLIGENCE	Matthijs de Zwaan (Coordinator Research Intelligence, VU), Rik Iping (Strategic Advisor, Erasmus MC)	This episode speculates about the ideal future of research intelligence in 2030, focusing on technological trends like AI and scientific network structures while addressing technological developments and historical challenges.	2023-03-19	77
UB2030 - FUTURE OF OPEN SCIENCE	Sander Bos (Open Science Coordinator, VU), Ludo Waltman (Deputy Director, CWTS Leiden)	Explores the significance of Open Science and envisions a future where science is accessible, inclusive, coordinated, and innovative. Key topics include open access, community building, and the balance between technology and inclusivity.	2023-05-21	105
UB2030 - FUTURE OF RESEARCH SUPPORT	Joeri Both (VU Amsterdam), Aaron Tay (Singapore University of Management)	Discusses the evolving role of libraries in supporting increasingly complex research environments, the need for technological expertise, and the library's transition to being expertise networks within universities.	2023-03-19	63
UB2030 - FUTURE OF DIGITAL SERVICES AND INFRASTRUCTURE	Alexey Pristupa (Head of Digital Services, VU UB), Alistair Dunning (Head of Research Services, TU Delft)	Explores the future of digital library services and infrastructures, focus on trust, openness, and inspiration	2023-08-08	79
UB2030 - FUTURE OF EDUCATION SUPPORT	Cees van Gent (Head of Education Support), Rens van der Vorst (Technophilosopher)	Discusses the importance of human-centred education, the evolving role of technology in education, and the challenges of redefining educational values and methods to promote personal development and authentic learning.	2024-03-26	66
UB2030 - FUTURE OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS	August den Hollander (Professor of Religious Heritage, VU), Michiel Cock (Head of Special Collections, VU)	Discusses the intersection of heritage and technology, the potential of digital collections, and the importance of inclusivity in preserving and presenting heritage, emphasising both digital and physical experiences.	2024-05-21	39
UB2030 - FUTURE OF INFORMATION SERVICES	Head of Information Services UB.VU. Jan Struiksma, Emeritus professor of Administrative Law VU University Amsterdam	Explores the role of AI in education, focusing on its impact on research, learning, and teaching, while addressing challenges like accessibility, copyright, sustainability, and the evolving role of libraries in supporting open access and digital tools.	2024-06-12	N/A
UB2030 - FUTURE OF LIBRARY AS PLACE	Aat Vos (Architect, Includi), Jan-Maarten Pauw (Head of Service Desk and Logistics, VU UB)	Examines the role of libraries as physical and digital meeting spaces, focusing on inclusivity, social interaction, and libraries as hubs for community engagement and knowledge sharing.	2024-04-02	101
UB2030 - FUTURE OF LIBRARY IN SOCIETY	Frank Kupper (Theatre Maker and Researcher, Athena Institute), Hilde van Wijngaarden (Director, VU UB)	Highlights the transformative role of libraries in fostering dialogue and knowledge sharing, emphasising their evolution towards open information dissemination and social engagement in science communication.	2024-04-02	32

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Key Recurring Themes:

1. 🤖 Use of AI; in Job Assistance & Automation, requiring Open Content and guardrails for Ethics, Sustainability and Equality
2. 🚀 Integrated and User-centric Digital Services
3. 🎓 Library education, training and skills development
4. 💬 Safe Place for Dialogue, Society and Science

THANKS

